

Synthesis of Thienyl Analogs of Substituted Flavonoids

K. A. THAKAR and P. R. MULEY

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad

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As a part of our scheme towards finding a relationship between the structure and biological activity, a number of new dialkyl, dihalogeno, alkyl-halogeno benzochromones and acrylophenones having 2-thienyl-heterocyclic substituent at 2- and 3-positions respectively have been prepared.

IN recent years increasing interest is being directed towards the synthesis of chromones and acrylophenones having heterocyclic substituents due to the physiological and/or biological properties associated with them. Thus chromones with heterocyclic substituents at 2-position are reported to possess bronchodilatory¹, coronary spasmolytic², CNS depressant⁴ and anti-sarcoma-180⁵ properties. Acrylophenones with heterocyclic substituents have exhibited antibacterial⁶, antitubercular⁷, antifungal⁸ and insecticidal⁹ properties. Though a number of such compounds are claimed to possess the properties mentioned, very little work towards the structure-activity relationship of such compounds, has so far been made. An attempt was, therefore, made to find such relationship between the two. As a first step towards such a study, a number of acrylophenones and chromones having disubstituents like alkyl-alkyl, halogeno-halogeno, alkyl-halogeno, benzo and 2-thienyl ring were prepared. The modification in the structure of these compounds was also made by changing the positions of these substituents.

The following 2'-hydroxyacetophenones which were required as starting materials were prepared by following the general methods given in literature :

1. 3':4'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10a}
2. 3':5'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy acetophenone ^{10b} and ^{10c}
3. 4':5'-Dichloro 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10a}
4. 4':6'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10d}
5. 3':4'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10e,10f}
6. 3':5'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10g}
7. 4':5'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10h}
8. 4':6'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.¹⁰ⁱ
9. 4'Chloro-5'-methyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone^{10b}

10. 3':5'-Dibromo-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10j,10k}
11. 3':4'-Benzo-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone.^{10l}

The disubstituted 2'-hydroxyacetophenones were esterified with thenoyl chloride. The thenoyloxy esters (IA-XIA) thus obtained were converted into 1:3 propanediones (IB-XIB) by Baker-Venkatraman transformation. The cyclodehydration of these 1:3 propanediones in acidic medium afforded the substituted chromones (IC-XIC).

Base catalysed condensations of all the substituted 2'-hydroxy acetophenones excepting 3':4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone with thiophene-2-aldehyde yielded the corresponding 3-(2-thienyl) acrylophenones (IID-XID). The condensation product of 3':4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone with thiophene-2-aldehyde (ID) did not respond to the characteristic reactions of acrylophenones and hence it was considered to be a flavanone derivative. It was insoluble in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and gave no colouration with neutral ferric chloride reagent. Bromine absorption was very slow and that too with the evolution of hydrogen bromide which could be detected with the help of ammonia.

These acrylophenones underwent oxidative ring closure with selenium dioxide to the same chromones (IIE-XIE) as obtained by the cyclodehydration of 1:3 propanediones (IB-XI B). The identity was proved by taking their mixed melting points which showed no depression.

The acrylophenones (IID-XID) under Algarflyn-Oyamada¹¹⁻¹⁷ reaction conditions gave the substituted 2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones(IIE-XIE).

- I, A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_2 = CH_3$ and $R_3, R_4 = H$.
- II, A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_3 = CH_3$ and $R_2, R_4 = H$.
- III, A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_4 = H$ and $R_2, R_3 = CH_3$.
- IV A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_3 = H$ and $R_2, R_4 = CH_3$.
- V A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_2 = Cl$ and $R_3, R_4 = H$.
- VI A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_3 = Cl$ and $R_2, R_4 = H$.
- VII A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_4 = H$ and $R_2, R_3 = Cl$.
- VIII A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_3 = H$ and $R_2, R_4 = Cl$.
- IX A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_4 = H$, R_2, CH_3 and $R_3 = Cl$.
- X A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_3 = Br$ and $R_2, R_4 = H$.
- IX A,B,C,D & E : $R_1, R_2 = Benzo$ and $R_3, R_4 = H$.
and $R = 2$ -Thienyl

Experimental

Preparation of substituted 2'-(2-thienyloxy) acetophenones : (IA-XIA) Table 1 : A mixture of substituted 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone (0.01 mole) and thenoyl chloride (0.011 mole), was treated dropwise with anhydrous pyridine (5 ml) with shaking. The mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured over ice and hydrochloric acid.

The separated solid was filtered and washed successively with water, dilute sodium hydroxide solution (2%) and water. The dry solid was crystallised from alcohol. The yield of the ester was 70%.

Preparation of substituted 1:3-propanediones (IB-XIB) Table 2 : To a solution of substituted 2'-(2-thienyloxy) acetophenone (0.01 mole) in anhydrous pyridine (10 ml), was added powdered potassium hydroxide (0.03 mole). The mixture was stirred for half an hour at room temperature. The yellow paste formed was diluted with water and poured over crushed ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated yellow solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised from either alcohol or acetic acid as solvent. The yield varied from 60-70%.

Preparation of substituted 2-(2-thienyl) chromones (IC-XIC) Table 3 : A solution of 1-(substituted 2'-hydroxy-phenyl) 3-(2-thienyl) 1:3-propanedione (1 gm) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 ml), was refluxed for half an hour. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered and washed successively with water, dilute sodium hydroxide solution and with water again. It was then crystallised by using proper solvent. The yield of the substituted chromone varied from 50-60%.

Preparation of substituted 3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenones : (ID-XID) Table 4 : To an ice cold solution of substituted 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone (0.01 mole) and thiophen-2-aldehyde (0.012 mole) in ethyl alcohol (20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring a 40% solution of potassium hydroxide (10 ml), over a period of 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured over crushed ice and hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. The dry solid was crystallised by using proper solvent. All the substituted 2'-hydroxy-acetophenone excepting 3':4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-acetophenone, condensed with thiophene-2-aldehyde to give the condensation products which showed the characteristic reactions of acrylophenones. As stated earlier the condensation product with 3':4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy acetophenone did not respond to the characteristic reactions of acrylophenone. It was, therefore, assumed to be a substituted flavanone. The yield of the acrylophenones was from 70-80%.

Preparation of substituted 2-(2-thienyl)-chromones : A mixture of substituted 3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone (0.005 mole) selenium dioxide (1 gm) and amyl alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed at 160°C for fifteen hours in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and the selenium formed during the reaction was filtered off. The filtrate was washed with a 2% solution of sodium hydroxide in order to remove the unchanged acrylophenone. It was then steam distilled to remove amyl alcohol. The non-steam volatile solid was collected by filtration and was crystallised from proper solvent. The yield varied from 40-50%.

Preparation of substituted 2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones : (IIE-XIE) Table 5 : Substituted 3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenone (0.005 mole), was dissolved in methyl alcohol (25 ml) and 2% solution of sodium hydroxide (12 ml). The reaction flask was held in ice water and hydrogen peroxide (40 vol. 12 ml) was added in portions with shaking. The flask was loosely stoppered and kept at room temperature for 6-8 hours, when the red colour of the reaction mixture changed to lemon yellow. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice and hydrochloric acid. The separated solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised by using proper solvent. The yield of the products was 30-50%.

TABLE 1—SUBSTITUTED 2'-(2-THENYOXY) ACETOPHENONES (IA-XIA)

Acetophenones	M.P. °C	Crystallisation solvent.	Found		Required	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
IA 3':4'-Dimethyl-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	109	Alcohol	66.28	5.63	65.68	5.11
IIA 3':5'-Dimethyl-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	79	Aq. Alcohol	65.86	4.60	65.68	5.11
IIIA 4':5'-Dimethyl-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	85	"	65.36	4.51	65.68	5.11
IVA 4':6'-Dimethyl-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	85	"	65.25	5.10	65.68	5.11
VA 3':4'-Dichloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	117	Alcohol	49.75	2.82	49.52	2.53
VIA 3':5'-Dichloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	77	Alcohol	49.40	2.61	49.52	2.53
VIIA 4':5'-Dichloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	104	"	49.67	2.20	49.52	2.53
VIIIA 4':6'-Dichloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	92	Aq. Alcohol	49.63	2.42	49.52	2.53
IXA 4'-Methyl-5'-chloro-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	107	"	57.72	3.67	57.25	3.73
XA 3':5'-Dibromo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	94	Alcohol	38.58	2.00	38.61	1.98
XIA 3':4'-Benzo-2'-(2-thienyloxy)-	142	Aq. Alcohol	69.44	4.22	68.91	4.05

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED 1:3-PROPANEDIONES (IB-XIB)

1:3 Propanediones		M.P. °C	Crystallisation solvent.	Found		Required	
				C%	H%	C%	H%
IB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':4'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	113	Alcohol	65.19	4.93	65.68	5.11
IIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':5'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	81	"	65.27	4.99	65.68	5.11
IIIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(4':5'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	114	"	65.34	5.05	65.68	5.11
IVB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(4':6'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	119	"	66.00	4.64	65.68	5.11
VB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':4'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	172	"	49.12	2.81	49.52	2.53
VIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	138	"	49.98	2.89	49.52	2.53
VIIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(4':5'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	188	Acetic acid	49.14	2.79	49.52	2.53
VIIIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(4':6'-dichloro-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	111	Alcohol	50.00	2.82	49.52	2.53
IXB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(4'-methyl-5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	131	"	56.71	3.36	57.05	3.73
XB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':5'-dibromo-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	99	"	38.50	2.36	38.63	1.98
XIB	1-(2-thienyl)-3-(3':4'-benzo-2'-hydroxy-phenyl)-	132	Acetic acid	68.50	4.03	68.91	4.05

TABLE 3—SUBSTITUTED 2-(2-THIENYL)-CHROMONES (IC-XIC)

Chromone	M.P. °C	Crystallisation solvent	Found		Required		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	
IC	7:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	159	Aq. alcohol	69.94	4.44	70.33	4.69
IIC	6:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	181	Alcohol	70.55	4.35	70.33	4.69
IIIC	6:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	164	Alcohol	70.81	5.14	70.33	4.69
IVC	5:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	159	Alcohol + acetic acid	70.73	4.53	70.33	4.69
VC	7:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	213	Alcohol	52.19	1.84	52.52	2.02
VIC	6:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	196	Alcohol	52.03	1.93	52.52	2.02
VIIC	6:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	228	Acetic acid	52.12	2.01	52.52	2.02
VIIIC	5:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	202	Alcohol	52.73	1.95	52.52	2.02
IXC	6-Chloro-7-methyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	166	Alcohol	60.27	3.40	60.75	3.25
XC	6:8-Dibromo-2-(2-thienyl)-	187	Alcohol	40.04	1.58	40.41	1.55
XIC	7:8-Benzo-2-(2-thienyl)-	173	Aq. alcohol	73.03	3.23	73.38	3.59

TABLE 4—SUBSTITUTED 2-(2-THIENYL)-FLAVANONE (ID)- AND SUBSTITUTED 3-(2-THIENYL)-ACRYLOPHENONES (IID - XID).

Acrylophenones	M.P. °C	Crystallisation solvent.	Found		Required		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	
ID	7:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-flavanone.	209	Acetic acid	69.52	5.03	69.77	5.43
IID	3':5'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-3[(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone.	108	Alcohol	69.31	5.01	69.77	5.43
IIID	4':5'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone	112	Alcohol	70.03	5.81	69.77	5.43
IVD	4':6'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone	120	Aq. Alcohol	69.71	5.54	69.77	5.43
VD	3':4'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone.	166	Acetic acid	51.93	2.99	52.17	2.67
VID	3':5'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl) - acrylophenone.	171	Acetic acid	51.86	2.35	52.17	2.67
VIID	4':5'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone	134	Alcohol + acetic acid	52.44	3.15	52.17	2.67
VIIID	4':6'-Dichloro-2'-hydroxy-3(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone	119	Alcohol	51.52	2.52	52.17	2.67
IXD	4'-Methyl-5'-chloro-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone.	118	Alcohol	60.73	3.89	60.32	3.95
XD	3':5'-Dibromo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone.	162	Acetic acid	39.86	2.30	40.21	2.06
XID	3':4'-Benzo-2'-hydroxy-3-(2-thienyl)- acrylophenone.	149	Alcohol	72.35	4.34	72.85	4.29

TABLE 5—SUBSTITUTED 2-(2-THIENYL)-3-HYDROXY-CHROMONES. (IIE - XIIE)

3-hydroxy-chromone	M.P. °C	Crystallisaion solvent.	Found		Required		
			C%	H%	C%	H%	
IIE	6:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	238	Alcohol + acetic acid	66.25	4.07	66.17	4.41
IIIE	6:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	208	Alcohol	66.46	4.25	66.17	4.41
IVE	5:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	202	Alcohol + acetic acid	66.72	3.90	66.17	4.41
VE	7:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	216	Acetic acid	49.75	1.55	49.84	1.92
VIIE	6:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	221	Alcohol + acetic acid	49.86	1.55	49.84	1.92
VIIIE	6:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	234	Acetic acid	50.33	1.54	49.84	1.92
VIIIIE	5:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	218	Aq. Acetic acid	49.51	1.78	49.84	1.92
IXIE	6-Chloro-7-methyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	211	Acetic acid	57.10	2.97	57.43	3.08
XIE	6:8-Dibromo-2-(2-thienyl)	256	Acetic acid	39.13	1.27	38.81	1.49
XIIE	7:8-Benzo-2-(2-thienyl)-	241	Acetic acid	69.52	3.19	69.39	3.40

Infrared Spectral Data

Infrared spectra of a few substituted 2-(2-thienyl)- and 2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy chromones were taken using Perkin-Elmer infracord. The spectral data of these compounds are presented in the ir Table 1 and 2 respectively. In the spectra of these compounds the characteristic absorption frequencies for the groups $-C=O$, $-C=C-$, $C-O-C$ and 2-thienyl, were observed

Activity Reports

The compounds such as 1:3-propanediones, 3-(2-thienyl)-acrylophenones, 2-(2-thienyl)-chromones and 2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones were tested for gastric acid secretion-pylorus ligation, gastric-bicarbonate-ATP ase in vitro, Adjuvant-Induced Arthritis and parasitological (N.dubius and H.nana) activities. None of these compounds showed any significant activity.

IR Table 1

Chromone	$\nu C=O$ cm^{-1}	$\nu C=C$ cm^{-1}	$\nu C-O-C$ cm^{-1}	ν 2-thienyl cm^{-1}
1. 7:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1620	1585	1240 1370	750
2. 6:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1640	1590	1240 1360	760
3. 6:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1635	1600	1220 1360	715
4. 7:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1640	1665 1600	1232 1370	760
5. 6:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1650	1565 1600	1237 1380	730
6. 6:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1650	1570 1610	1240 1380	710
7. 7:8-Benzo-2-(2-thienyl)-	1650	1580 1610	1237 1390	714

IR Table 2

3-Hydroxy-chromone	$\nu C=O$ cm^{-1}	$\nu C=C$ cm^{-1}	$\nu C-O-C$ cm^{-1}	$\nu-OH$ cm^{-1}	ν 2-thienyl cm^{-1}
1. 7:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1600	1550	1295 1220	3100	720
2. 6:8-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1600	1550	1300 1210	3150	725
3. 6:7-Dichloro-2-(2-thienyl)-	1600	1500	1300 1215	3200	710
4. 7:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1600	1550	1300 1210	3200	725
5. 6:8-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1625	1585	1295 1208	3150	720
6. 6:7-Dimethyl-2-(2-thienyl)-	1625	1565	1285 1208	3200	730
7. 7:8-Benzo-2-(2-thienyl)-	1625	1565	1300 1220	3200	715

in the expected regions. The spectra of substituted 2-(2-thienyl)-3-hydroxy-chromones (IR Table 2) showed the hydroxyl absorption band in the region 3200-3300 cm^{-1} . This lowering in hydroxyl absorption frequency, as compared with the expected value, may be attributed to chelation with the carbonyl group. The chelation of the hydroxyl group with the carbonyl group has also, in turn, affected the $-C=O$ absorption frequency in such compounds. Thus as seen in the IR Table 2 the $-C=O$ absorption frequency in such compounds has appeared at a slightly lower value as compared with the similar absorption in 2-(2-thienyl)-chromones (IR Table 1). The frequency shift in the carbonyl absorption due to chelation is of the order of 20 to 40 cm^{-1} .

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